

Simultaneous Transport of Aqueous Solutes in Four Soils of West Bengal

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Coupled osmotic transport processes involving passage of aqueous CuSO_4 , KH_2PO_4 and NH_4Cl in four soils of contrasting properties have been studied. The resulting reflection coefficient, mechanical filtration capacity and solute permeability for various transport systems have been related generally to the contents of clay and presence or absence of micaceous illitic minerals in the clay fractions of the soils. The relevant hydrodynamic frictional coefficients have been used to describe the decoupling of solute and solvent during the given osmotic flows, leading to salt accumulation down the soil profile.

In a dynamic polycomponent system like soil, coupling between various transport processes occurring simultaneously often leads to a flow of one kind from a non-conjugate force. Such coupled processes are of interest not only from theoretical viewpoint but from practical considerations as well, especially so far irrigated arid and semi-arid soils of high salt contents. De and Sanyal¹ discussed the usefulness of the thermodynamic approach in studying these processes.

While summarising the various studies examining simultaneous (isothermal) transport of salt and water in soil/plant systems, an overwhelming emphasis on the quantitative aspect does not escape one's attention, leaving much to be desired in terms of the qualitative information that may emerge from these studies. In the present communication, an attempt is made to highlight the significance of these relatively less discussed qualitative parameters in characterising solute-water-soil interactions in isothermal coupled transport processes in soils. The systems studied cover isothermal transport of aqueous CuSO_4 , KH_2PO_4 and NH_4Cl in four soils of contrasting properties.

Theoretical: The dissipation function (ϕ) for transport across a soil plug, separating two aqueous solutions having different concentrations that permit an osmotic flow with a concomitant build-up of hydrostatic pressure difference, may be expressed as²

$$\phi = J_V \nabla p + J_D \nabla \pi \quad (1)$$

where, ∇ refers to gradient across the plug, J_V the volume flux, J_D the diffusion flux and p and π are the hydrostatic (mechanical) and osmotic pressure respectively. Indeed, J_D may be regarded as that measuring velocity of solute (V_s) relative to that of water (V_w), and hence its name, while J_V may be reduced to a velocity of the solvent (V_w)²,

$$J_D = V_s - V_w \quad (2)$$

and

$$J_V = V_w \quad (3)$$

The linear phenomenological equations are then obtained as³

$$J_V = L_P \nabla p + L_{PD} \nabla \pi \quad (4)$$

$$J_D = L_{DP} \nabla p + L_D \nabla \pi \quad (5)$$

The fluxes refer to the soil plug reference frame so that $J_M = 0$, identically. Here L_P is the mechanical filtration capacity of the plug, L_D the diffusional mobility per unit osmotic pressure difference, L_{PD} is identified with the coefficient of osmotic flow and L_{DP} the ultrafiltration coefficient of the plug. Provided that these fluxes and forces are properly chosen, Onsager's Reciprocity Relations (ORR) hold good, namely, in this case, $L_{DP} = L_{PD}$. By a series of transformations, it was shown³ that the reflection coefficient (σ)⁴ is given by

$$\sigma = 1 - \left(\frac{V_s}{V_w} \right)_{\Delta\pi=0} = - \frac{L_{PD}}{L_P} = \left(\frac{\nabla p}{\nabla \pi} \right)_{J_V=0} \quad (6)$$

For an ideally semipermeable plug, $V_s = 0$, and $\sigma = 1$, whereas for an open plug, $V_s = V_w$ and $\sigma = 0$ (eqn. 6).

Following the procedure adopted by the Kedem and Katchalsky⁵, the linear phenomenological equations (eqns. 4 and 5) can be further transformed to

$$J_V = L_P (\nabla p - \sigma \Delta \pi) \quad (7)$$

and

$$J_s = w \Delta \pi + \bar{C}_s (1 - \sigma) J_V \quad (8)$$

where, J_s stands for the solute flux and w , the solute permeability, is given by

$$w = \left(\frac{J_s}{\nabla \pi} \right)_{J_V=0} = \frac{\bar{C} (L_P L_D - L_{PD}^2)}{L_P} \quad (9)$$

\bar{C}_s being the average solute concentrations in the solutions separated by the plug. On measuring J_V for various ∇p applied across the plug at a constant $\nabla \pi$, and on plotting the resulting J_V values against the corresponding ∇p 's, a straight-line is expected (eqn. 7). From the slope and the intercept of the latter, L_P and σ are obtained. For determining w , the steady state condition, namely $J_V = 0$, is enforced on the transport system across the plug by way of adjusting the hydrostatic pressure gradient, ∇p (see later), and equation (9) is resorted to for computation of w .

With the values of L_p , σ and w at hand, the solute rejection performance of the soil (as in a hyperfiltration process) can be assessed using the formalism developed by Johnson *et al.*⁶. The solute rejection parameter (r) is given as

$$F = \frac{(\sigma - r)}{\sigma(1-r)} \quad (10)$$

where the flow parameter F is so related to J_v that as J_v becomes large, F tends to zero so that the reflection coefficient (σ) is the limiting value attainable by r when filtration overtakes diffusion (eqn. 10). The data on σ , L_p and w can be further utilised to assess the efficiency of the soils and clays for solute rejection in course of solute accumulation in the soil profile. The criteria developed by Speigler and Kedem⁷, involving various hydrodynamic frictional coefficients, are made use of. Thus, for efficient rejection,

$$f_{sm} \gg f_{wm} \quad (11)$$

$$f_{sm} \gg f_{sw} \quad (12)$$

where, f represents friction between the species indicated by the subscripts, s (solute), w (water) and m (plug). The frictional coefficients are obtained by substituting the values of different parameters in the following equations,

$$L_p = \frac{\phi_w \bar{V}_w}{f_{wm}} \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma = 1 - \frac{K_s f_{sw}}{(f_{sw} + f_{sm}) \phi_w} \quad (14)$$

$$W = \frac{K_s}{(f_{sw} + f_{sm})} \quad (15)$$

where, ϕ_w , \bar{V}_w and K_s denote respectively, the volume fraction of water in soil, partial molal volume of water, and the distribution coefficient of the solute between the soil and the aqueous phase.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

Location of soil	pH (1 : 2.5)	E.C. (1 : 5) dS m ⁻¹	Organic carbon g kg ⁻¹	Clay %	C.E.C. cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹
Chinsurah ^a	7.4	0.30	10.7	64.8	36.5
Canning ^a	6.7	4.80	4.64	59.8	21.2
Mohitnagar ^b	6.0	0.17	19.2	24.8	23.7
Jhargram ^c	5.3	0.18	2.21	22.2	10.9

*Soil order: ^aentisol, ^bmollisol, ^calfisol.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the important physicochemical properties as well as the dominant clay minerals present in the four soils used. Table 2 gives the mineralogical make-up of the clay fractions of the given soils. Representative plots of J_v vs ∇P for the Jhargram soil is presented in Fig. 1.

The data on transport parameters for flow of the given electrolyte solutions through the soils studied are shown in Table 3. For each solute, σ value was found to be the lowest in the Jhargram soil and the highest in the Chin-

surah soil. This trend may be related to those of clay content and hence generally the C.E.C. of these soils (Tables 1 and 2) in which the latter soil was the richest and the former the poorest. However, the presence in the Mohitnagar soil, rich in soil organic matter, of strongly binding organoaluminium polymeric cations in the interlayer space (e.g. the brucite type of layers of chlorite minerals; see Tables 1 and 2) may effectively oppose cationic exchange in course of permeation of the given aqueous electrolytes through the Mohitnagar soil⁸. This will bring down the σ values in the given soil despite its quite appreciable C.E.C., as observed in the present study (Table 3). The same is less true for the Jhargram soil, the only other acidic soil studied, which is much poorer in soil organic matter (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Plot of volume flux against applied pressure gradient for three aqueous solutions in the Jhargram soil.

However, essentially kaolinitic nature of this soil (Table 2) would also help bring down the given σ values (see below).

For the bivalent Cu^{2+} salt, in general, and the K-salt in particular, such order of σ values may also be related to the nature of the dominant clay mineral and the general clay mineralogical make-up of the given soils (Tables 1 and 2). Thus, the Jhargram soil was dominated, as stated above, by kaolinite of practically no specific sites for K, while the illitic clays of the Chinsurah soil were known to possess a high degree of specificity for K. Similar considerations apply to the other two soils which were intermediate in nature. The cationic binding energy on clays would, in general, also be higher for bivalent cations compared to monovalent ones. The order of L_p values, which measure the mechanical permeability of the soils, could also be related inversely to the clay content of the soils studied (Table 1) as one would expect. The solute permeability (w) follows similar trends, in general.

On examining the frictional coefficient values f_{wm} , f_{sm} and f_{sw} (Table 3), the latter are seen to satisfy the inequalities given in equations (11) and (12). In particular, the inequality, $f_{sm} > f_{sw}$ (eqn. 12), suggests that there will be decoupling of solute and water fluxes in the soil plug, causing solute accumulation in the soil profile⁸. The degree of the above inequality being much narrower in the Jhargram soil, as compared to that in, for instance, the Chinsurah soil, the latter will be more prone to solute accumulation down the profile, especially for Cu-salts (Table 3). In course of such decoupling, the maximum accumulation attainable (i.e. the solute rejection coefficient, r ; see eqn. 10) will obviously be the corresponding σ value, which is also the highest in the Chinsurah soil for each solute. The σ values for the solutes studied in each soil follow the order : $\text{CuSO}_4 > \text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4 > \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$. A somewhat higher σ for CuSO_4 than that of KH_2PO_4 in each soil (Table 3) may possibly be related to a greater tendency for ion-pair formation in the soil phase for CuSO_4 than that for KH_2PO_4 at the given soil pH values. The former enhances the lag between the solute and the solvent fluxes, and hence raises the σ value (see eqn. 6).

TABLE 2—MINERALOGICAL MAKE-UP OF THE CLAY FRACTION OF THE SOILS*

Location of soil	(M)	(Ch)	(I-Ch)	(I)	(K)	(S)
Chinsurah	-	17	-	18	6	49
Canning	-	15	-	40	5	30
Mohitnagar	-	40.0	42.9	-	17.1	-
Jhargram	-	-	-	36.3	63.7	-

* (M) = Montmorillonite; (Ch) = chlorite; (I-Ch) = illite + chlorite; (I) = illite; (K) = kaolinite; (S) = smectite.

TABLE 3—TRANSPORT PARAMETERS AND FRICTIONAL COEFFICIENTS ($\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) FOR TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS CuSO_4 , KH_2PO_4 AND NH_4Cl IN THE SOILS

Soil	σ	L_p cm s^{-1}	w $\times 10^9 \text{ mol cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	f_{wm} $\times 10^{-5}$	f_{sm} $\times 10^{-8}$	f_{sw} $\times 10^{-8}$
Aqueous CuSO_4 :						
Chinsurah	0.91	4.14×10^{-7}	7.43	123.0	0.67	0.28
Canning	0.88	1.87×10^{-6}	8.02	39.0	0.42	0.21
Mohitnagar	0.71	7.54×10^{-5}	9.12	1.11	0.31	0.18
Jhargram	0.62	5.27×10^{-4}	9.49	0.63	0.14	0.09
Aqueous KH_2PO_4 :						
Chinsurah	0.86	4.2×10^{-7}	0.32	257	1.74	0.42
Canning	0.82	0.60×10^{-6}	0.45	126	1.93	0.51
Mohitnagar	0.58	0.78×10^{-5}	0.69	6.92	0.87	0.61
Jhargram	0.51	0.42×10^{-4}	2.53	0.64	2.97	2.72
Aqueous NH_4Cl :						
Chinsurah	0.57	9.02×10^{-7}	5.55	138.4	0.81	0.41
Canning	0.53	9.78×10^{-6}	6.41	19.4	0.62	0.31
Mohitnagar	0.48	4.67×10^{-5}	7.99	1.21	0.31	0.22
Jhargram	0.40	2.00×10^{-4}	8.92	0.69	0.17	0.12

Experimental

The design of the cell (Fig. 2) was an adaptation of that described by Srivastava⁹. Transport of aqueous CuSO_4 ,

KH_2PO_4 and NH_4Cl was studied in four surface (0–0.15 m) soils of West Bengal, namely, the soil samples from Chinsurah (Entisol), Canning (Entisol), Mohitnagar (Mollisol) and Jhargram (Alfisol). The clay content in the soils was determined by the Buoycos hydrometer method¹⁰.

An aqueous solution of the solute under study (concentration : 0.0002 N) was filled in the compartment-C while distilled water in compartment-D, with the desired

Fig. 2. Horizontal osmotic cell : T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ are stopcocks; M₁, M₂, magnetic stirrers; K, soil plug (thickness 1 cm, area 109 cm²); S, sintered glass disc of porosity G-4; L₁ L₂, capillary tube (19 cm × dia. 0.0138 cm); volume of the compartments C and D, 288 and 312 ml respectively.

soil in between the glass discs (S, S) at a given compaction and moisture content (Fig. 1). The system was allowed to stand for sometime. As soon as recession in the capillary-L₁L₂ due to osmosis was noticed, known pressure was applied on the solution compartment-C by adjusting the hydrostatic pressure head, and the rate of advancement of the liquid meniscus in L₁L₂ was noted with time. Since the back-flow of water into the solution compartment due to osmosis was generally quite small, the value of $\nabla\pi$ could be taken to be more or less constant during a particular run. The volume flux (J_v) for a given ∇P at a constant $\nabla\pi$ was calculated from the experimental data. Before the start of a fresh measurement, corresponding to another value of ∇P , the electrolyte solution in chamber-C was replaced with a fresh stock solution. The J_v values obtained were plotted against the corresponding ∇P according to eqn. (7) leading to values of L_p and σ from slope and intercept of linear plots. The experiments were conducted at 35°.

For determination of w according to eqn. (9), the aqueous solution of a given solute (known concentration) was filled in the compartment-C and distilled water in the compartment-D at 35°. The condition $J_v = 0$ was enforced on the system by adjusting the pressure-head attached to the solution compartment. The solutions in the two compartments were vigorously stirred with magnetic stirrers (M₁, M₂). After a known period of time, aliquots from the two compartments were withdrawn and analysed by the ap-

appropriate analytical techniques. The data were used to compute J_s and $\nabla\pi$ (which was an average value of the initial and final $\nabla\pi$ values) at $J_v = 0$, which were fitted to eqn. (9) leading to W .

Solute distribution coefficient (K_s): A given amount of soil was mixed with a known volume of the electrolytic solution having a known concentration. The contents were well-stirred for several days using a magnetic stirrer. The supernatant liquid was finally analysed to compute the amount of solute lost to the soil phase. The concentrations of the electrolytic solutes chosen were within the range of concentrations used in the osmotic experiments. The data were used to compute K_s for CuSO_4 , KH_2PO_4 and NH_4Cl for the four soil used.

Frictional coefficients : The data on L_p , σ , w , K_s and ϕ_w (obtained by independent experiments for the four soils studied) were fitted to equations (13–15) to obtain the hydrodynamic frictional coefficients, namely, f_{wm} , f_{sw} and f_{sm} for each soil-transport system.

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